

ONOMASTICS IS A BRANCH OF LINGUISTICS. USAGE OF ONOMASTICS IN LITERARY TEXTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7440033>

Abstract. *Onomastics is a branch of linguistics that studies any famous names, the history of their origin and change, as well as the sum of all famous names. In some studies, the term "onomastics" is also used in the sense of anthroponymy. Onomastics aims to identify and study existing onomastic systems.*

Keywords: *linguistics, name, onomastics, system, anthroponymy.*

ОНОМАСТИКА — РАЗДЕЛ ЯЗЫКОЗНАНИЯ. ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ОНОМАСТИКИ В ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННЫХ ТЕКСТАХ

Аннотация. *Ономастика - это раздел лингвистики, изучающий любые известные имена, историю их происхождения и изменения, а также сумму всех известных имен. В некоторых исследованиях термин «ономастика» также используется в смысле антропонимии. Ономастика направлена на выявление и изучение существующих ономастических систем.*

Ключевые слов: *лингвистика, имя, ономастика, система, антропонимия.*

Onomastics consists of the following sections according to the categories of objects that have received famous names: anthroponymics - famous names of people; toponymy - popular names of geographical objects; te - onimika - the names of gods, goddesses, religious-mythical persons and creatures according to various religious ideas; zoonymics - names given to animals (conditionally); cosmonomics - the names of regions of space, galaxies, constellations, etc., which are common in scientific circulation and among the people; astronomy — studies the names of some celestial bodies (planets and stars). In addition to the above, onomastics has several other divisions. Onomastics divides real names into realonyms (names of existing or existing objects) and mythonyms (names of imaginary objects).

Onomastics is divided into literary and dialectal, usual (practical) and poetic, contemporary and historical, theoretical and practical types depending on the linguistic characteristics of famous names. Theoretical onomastics studies the emergence of famous names in language and speech, literary and dialectal fields, the basis of nomination (naming), development, various changes in this process, their use in speech, distribution in certain regions and languages, and their structural structure. The study of poetic names in literary texts (poetic Onomastics) is a special problem. Onomastics is also a comparative-historical, structural, genetic, areal, onomastic mapping of linguistics, etc. using methods, phonetic, morphological, word formation, semantic, etymological, etc. learns aspects.

Practical onomastics: transcription and transliteration of names belonging to foreign languages, identification of traditional (according to pronunciation and spelling), translatable and non-translatable names, preparation of instructions on how to write "foreign" names in one's own language, creation of new words from names acquired from foreign languages b-n, name deals with issues of giving and changing names.

Onomastics is interrelated with such disciplines as history, archeology, genealogy, heraldry, textual studies, literary studies, astronomy, demography. Anthroponyms, as an

important part of the language system, reflect the uniqueness of the national consciousness and social development of society. The semantics of anthroponyms is studied from the point of view of referentiality, which is presented as the main differential sign of a noun. As the oldest units of any language system, proper nouns are one of the most interesting and complex linguistic universals. All the linguistic, semantic, cognitive, pragmatic, cultural definitions given in the scientific literature to this day regarding the nature of the famous noun-anthroponym are controversial to one degree or another. Difficulties in defining the semantic structure of anthroponyms in linguistics, including French linguistics, led to the widespread opinion about anthroponyms as "incorrect", units that do not have full lexical value, which are on the edge of the language system, and, accordingly, they were forgotten as a subject of linguistic analysis. Therefore, the science of anthroponyms - anthroponymics - developed for a long time, separated from the main directions of linguistics, and described the name fund of the language in historical, etymological and regional aspects. It is true that complex theoretical issues related to the study of the linguistic nature of anthroponyms have been raised from time to time, but many of them remain without satisfactory explanation. The reason for this is that the meaning of the anthroponym has not been resolved at the methodological and philosophical level. Famous nouns are among the language tools that provide the opportunity to convey a large amount of semantic and emotional content in a specially compact form. Uncovering the system of symbols, images, and associations associated with nouns constitutes the specific aspects of the linguistic nature of nouns. Prominent nouns are a separate group of nouns that perform a noun function, distinguishing individuals and individuals from other similar objects and events in the language. There is an opinion that an anthroponym as a linguistic unit denoting a single object has only an extensional meaning. However, researchers who recognize the existence of meaning in nouns support the thesis about the conceptual aspect of noun semantics. At the same time, the significant meaning of the anthroponym is interpreted as a categorical-abstract meaning that reflects the belonging of nouns to a certain class. For example, the significant meaning for names of people is limited to the realization of the general concept "person" (male/female). Thus, although the importance of subject-logical meaning is recognized in this approach, it should be noted that it is very abstract in nature. In anthroponymic semantics, the meaning of a single noun is undoubtedly the main meaning. This fact is determined in advance by its factual relevance to a concrete single object or mental image in real existence. It is the close connection between the anthroponym and the referent it signifies that prepares the ground for the extension of the anthroponym's interrelationship with the object. The characteristic of acquiring a generalized meaning is characteristic of anthroponyms, which are primarily associated with specific denotations. This feature is based on clear and strong connections between the name and a specific person and, accordingly, all permanent associations that arise through the distinguishing features of this person. The persistence of associations associated with a certain person allows the name of this person to be transferred to mean people who have the same characteristics as the first owner of this name. As a result of such generalized use of a personal name, the character of the concept expressed by the name changes. From the categorical-abstract it approaches the appellative. In this article, we focus on determining the place of the referential factor in the "unmodified" use of common nouns. Because, in contrast to the "metaphorical uses" of anthroponyms, their "exemplary uses" are, in most cases, indicated by similes and various interpretative means. The study of these cases allows to further improve the classification of

"exemplary uses" of personal names and surnames, to group "small families" of constructions. The "typical or unmodified" use of French anthroponyms appears in the text in the form of the construction un Np. In this construction, the adverbial noun defined by un(e) does not continue to indicate its usual or "primary" referent, as it does in standard, undefined usage. We cannot agree with the proposition that proper nouns should have no other modifiers, as we have sufficient linguistic facts to show that this proposition is unfounded. We will focus on this in our next work. The existence of the indefinite article in the use of the name and surname and the reference made to its original owner create many problematic situations. In such usage, the anthroponym can be both modified and unmodified at the same time. The possible confusion between figurative usage and metaphorical usage is preserved here: Cette nouvelle «cité sainte» ferait assuragement les délices d'un Umberto ECO. In this example, the microcontext of Umberto Eco corresponds to one of many possibilities of metaphorical use, while the reference of the anthroponym remains ambiguous: either Umberto Eco himself or another referent, and this referent's similarities with Umberto Eco are shown. On the basis of semantic referential interpretations, in our opinion, it will be possible to put an end to such ambiguity. A proper noun in modal use refers to the initial referent of that noun, that alone, while an anthroponym in metaphorical use refers to another referent. In other words, an exemplary usage is a usage without referential change and forms the bud of a metaphorical usage. Oftentimes, some constructs allow us to see the underlying ambiguity that characterizes exemplary usage. Comparative constructions can be included among such constructions, which show the boundary between exemplary use and metaphorical use in the context.

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